

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ADARSH bearing USN 6SU21IV001 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Virology and immunology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AGNAS M S bearing USN 6SU21IV002 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Virology and immunology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms DENIL TOMY bearing USN 6SU21IV003 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Virology and immunology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms PRATHANA VINU bearing USN 6SU21IV004 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Virology and immunology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SABANA SHERIN K P bearing USN 6SU21IV005 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Virology and immunology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHREYA P bearing USN 6SU21IV006 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Virology and immunology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SWATHI DAYAL NAMBIAR bearing USN 6SU21IV007 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Virology and immunology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms V AMRUTHA BABU bearing USN 6SU21IV008 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Virology and immunology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146